

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF VANISHING CREAME FOR THE TREATMENT OF PLAQUE PSORIASIS

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Article Received on 07 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 27 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17801463>

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How to cite this Article: *Arpit Sahu, Dr. Nidhi Bais, Dr. Sachin K. Jain, Dr. Sudha Vengrulerkar. (2025). Formulation And Evaluation Of Vanishing Creame For The Treatment Of Plaque Psoriasis. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 1047–1062. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Salicylic acid (SA) is a beta hydroxy acid and has multifunctional uses in the treatment of various diseases in skin such as acne, psoriasis, and photoaging. It exhibits the highest activity in the treatment of skin disease. In proposed work is to prepare vanishing cream formulations to treat skin psoriasis which is non-greasy and water removable, increasing patient's compliance and to study the effectiveness of the formulations in human volunteers in consultation with registered dermatologist. Various formulations of salicylic acids F1, F2, F3, F4, F5 was prepared. The prepared formulations was evaluated for different parameters. The drug content estimation showed uniform drug content in the all prepared formulations. *In-Vitro* drug release studies shows that, the formulation code F3 showed optimum release (51.28%) in 3 hours. All prepared

formulations did not segregate, ferment or physically deteriorated during storage and use at ambient temperature (30°C) for the period of six months. The studies revealed that the usage of vanishing cream bases formulations did not produce skin irritancy. On the observation no edema, erythema, inflammation or redness seen on the skin of both animals and human volunteers indicating formulations pass in the test of compatibility studies. It was revealed that salicylic acid vanishing cream formulation should be useful for treatment of scalp psoriasis.

KEYWORDS: Salicylic Acid, Plaque Psoriasis, Vanishing Creame, Skin Irritacy, In vitro drug release.

INTRODUCTION

Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory skin disorder that may drastically affect the quality of life of an affected person. Different treatments are available for psoriasis and among this topical therapy are most commonly used in majority of patients. Psoriasis has genetic and life style triggers, the treatment guidelines involve continuous monitoring and lifelong care for the patients. Knowledge of the disease trigger factors and their role in precipitating the psoriasis is quiet important in the disease management. Care should be taken to avoid these psoriasis triggers. In recent years, new therapies have been introduced and several existing treatments have been improved giving new hope to people with psoriasis.^[1]

Salicylic acid (SA) is a beta hydroxy acid and has multifunctional uses in the treatment of various diseases in skin such as acne, psoriasis, and photoaging. One problem often cited as associated with salicylic acid is that it can be quite irritating at pH 3-4, where it exhibits the highest activity in the treatment of skin disease.

Salicylic acid is the most effective keratolytic and found in several over the counter medicated shampoos and scalp solutions aimed at treatment of scalpas well as in compounded ointment helpful for psoriasis elsewhere on the body.

It is difficult to manage scalp psoriasis because treatment is unpleasant, generally produces in different results, only partial control and relapse rates are high.^[2]

The objective of present research work is to prepare vanishing cream of salicylic acid.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

MATERIALS

Salicylic Acid were obtained from Euphoria Healthcare Pvt. Ltd._Mumbai. Polyethylene glycol 400 from Ria International India. Octanol, Chloroform, Sodium hydroxide (NAOH), Potassium dihydrogen phosphate, Propylene glycol, Methyl Paraben, Propyl Paraben, Methanol from Merck HPLC grade and Paraffin wax from Kerax Limited.

METHOD

PREFORMULATION STUDY

A. Organoleptic properties

The drug sample was studied for organoleptic properties like color, odor, taste and crystallinity.^[3] The observation is shown in the table 2.

B. Melting point

Melting point of drug sample was determined by using melting point apparatus. The drug sample was taken and placed in a thin walled capillary tube, the tube was approximately 10-12 cm in length with 1mm in diameter and closed at one end. The capillary was placed in melting point apparatus and heated and when drug sample was melted the melting point of sample powder was recorded.^[4] The melting point of Salicylic Acid is shown in the table 3.

C. Partition Coefficient

Partition Coefficient of Salicylic Acid was determined by simple shaking flask method. 10 mg of drug was dissolved in 25 ml of distilled water and 25 ml of octanol in the separating flask. The flask was stoppered and shaken for 1 hr and kept aside for phase separation for at least 24 hrs to attain equilibrium. Two phases of octanol and water sample was separated by separating funnel. Aqueous phase containing Salicylic Acid was filtered through whatman filter paper. The filtered aliquote was measured spectrophotometrically after suitable dilution at 250 nm. The partition coefficient was measured by the given fomulea.^[5]

$$\log P_{\text{oct/wat}}^I = \log \left(\frac{[\text{solute}]_{\text{octanol}}^I}{[\text{solute}]_{\text{water}}^I} \right).$$

The value of partition coefficient is shown in the table: 4.

D. Identification of drug by

1. UV Spectroscopic Characterization

Estimation of salicylic acid in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer at $\lambda_{\text{max}}=233$ nm.

Preparation of standard curve in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer at $\lambda_{\text{max}}= 233$ nm.

Procedure for preparation of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer:

Solution-I: Dissolve 27.3 gm of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in 1000 ml of distilled water.

Solution-II: Dissolve 8.0 gm of sodium hydroxide in 1000 ml of distilled water

Mix 250 ml of solution -I with 174.5 ml of solution of solution-II and makeup volume up to 1000 ml with distilled water and adjust the pH if necessary.

Standard solution

Accurately weighted 25 mg of salicylic acid was dissolved in 25ml of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer to get a solution containing 1000mcg/ml.

Stock solution

From the standard stock, a stock solution was prepared to give a concentration of 40 mcg/ml in pH7.4 phosphate buffer. Aliquots of 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2 and 2.5 ml of stock solution of pipette out into 10ml volumetric flasks. The volume was made up to the mark with pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. These dilutions give 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 mcg/ml concentration of salicylic acid respectively. The absorbance of prepared solutions of salicylic acid in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer was taken at 233 nm in Shimadzu UV- 1700 spectrophotometer against an appropriate blank (pH 7.4 phosphate buffer).^[6] The UV spectrum of Salicylic Acid drug is shown in fig. 5.

2. Preparation of Calibration curve of Salicylic Acid

From the standard stock, a stock solution was prepared to give a concentration of 40mcg/ml in methanol. Aliquots of 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2 and 2.5ml of stock solution of pipette out into 10ml volumetric flasks. The volume was made up to the mark with methanol. These dilutions give 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 mcg/ml concentration of salicylic acid respectively. The absorbance of prepared solutions of salicylic acid in methanol were taken at 231.6nm in Shimadzu UV-1700 spectrophotometer against an appropriate blank (pH 7.4 phosphate buffer).^[7] The calibration curves of Salicylic Acid is shown in fig.6

E. Solubility studies of drug

Solubility of Salicylic Acid was determined in distilled water and various non-aqueous solvents like PEG 400, Propylene glycol, methanol, ethanol, chloroform, phosphate buffer 7.4. The various types of solubility studies include Qualitative solubility study and Quantitative super saturation solubility study.^[8]

FORMULATION AND DEVELOPMENT

Formulation of Vanishing Cream of Salicylic Acid

Table 1: Formulation of Vanishing Cream.

	S.No.	Ingredients	Quantity in gms.				
			F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Oilphase (A)	1.	Stearic acid	13.00	15.00	15.00	20.00	20.00

	2.	Stearyl alcohol	1.00	-	-	-	-
	3.	Cetyl alcohol	1.00	0.50	0.50	0.50	-
	4.	Potassium hydroxide	0.90	0.50	1.00	-	1.40
	5.	Sodium hydroxide	-	0.18	-	0.36	-
	6.	Propylene glycol	-	3.00	-	-	-
	7.	Triethanolamine	-	-	-	1.20	-
Aqueous phase (B)	8.	Glycerin	10.00	5.00	5.00	8.00	4.00
	9.	Propyl paraben	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
	10.	Methyl paraben	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
	11.	Purified water	67.95	69.67	72.35	63.79	68.45

- Vanishing creams are o/w emulsion based preparations containing aqueous phase and oil phase.
- Ingredients of oil phase (A) mixed together by melting in a china dish on constant stirring.
- Components of aqueous phase (B) mixed together and warmed to about same temperature of oil phase.
- Aqueous phase was added to oil phase drop by drop on constant stirring.
- The therapeutically active insoluble ingredient salicylic acid incorporated when the formulation begins to solidification by levigation method.
- The preservative propyl paraben and methyl paraben was added after cooling to 40°C.
- Each formulation contains 6 gm of salicylic acid.

Evaluation of optimized ointment formulations

A. Physical Examination

The prepared formulations were inspected visually for their color, odor, Appearance.^[7] The organoleptic characters of ointment are shown in table no. 7.

B. Determination of pH of ointment formulation

About 2.5 g of all formulations were taken in dry beaker and 50 ml of water was added. Beaker containing ointments was heated on water bath at 60–70°C. The pH of cream was determined using a pH meter. The determinations were carried out in triplicate and average of three readings were note.^[7] The pH of formulations are shown in the table 8.

C. Rheological Properties

Viscosity: The viscosity was determined by using Brookfield viscometer. The viscometer is placed on the "Standby Mode". Samples were allowed to reach room temperature and the

samples were shaken vigorously. Then the samples were filled in a 600-mL, low-form Griffin beaker at least 3/4 full of slurry from the sample bottle. The spindle number 64 was selected. The spindle was inserted in to the appropriate beaker containing sample. Care was to be taken to avoid air bubbles since it may be trapped beneath the spindle. The beaker was moved in to the position beneath the viscometer and the spindle was attached so that the spindle remains submerged into the sample. The sample viscosity is measured at 30°C. The reading was recorded in centipoises.^[8] The viscosity range of all the formulations are shown in the table 9.

D. Spreadability

Spreadability of the formulation was determined by an apparatus, which was suitably modified in the laboratory and used for the study. It consists of a wooden block, which was provided by a pulley at one end. A rectangular ground glass plate (20cm x 20cm) was fixed on the block. Two grams of the formulation was sandwiched between the ground fixed plates and another glass plate having the same dimensions of the fixed ground plate. The movable glass plate is provided with the hook. A 300gm weight was placed on the tip of two plates for five minutes to expel air and to provide a uniform film of the formulation between the plates. Excess of the formulation was scrapped off from the edges. The top plate was then subject to a pull of a 30 gms, initially with the help of a string attached to the hook and moves over the pulley. The time required by the top plate to move at a distance of 10 cms was noted. A shorter time interval indicates better spreadability.^[8]

The spreadability was calculated by using the formula

$$s = m \times l / t$$

s = spreadability

m = weight tied to the upper side

l = length of the glass slides

t = time taken in seconds

In case the slide did not move with 30 gms, weight was increased gradually. In case the slide was moving fastly, the weight was decreased gradually.

The spreadability of al the formulations are shown in the table 10.

E. Drug content

The drug equivalent to 50 mg of formulation was taken and dissolved in small quantity of methanol. Then the formulation is warmed on the water bath so that the drug present in the formulation was completely dissolved. Then the solution is filtered through Whattman filter

paper into 50 ml vol. flask. The volume is made up to the mark which gives concentration of 1000mcg/ml. From this different concentration of solution was taken in 10ml volumetric flask and volume was made upto 10 ml with methanol and absorbance was measured by UV spectrophotometer at 233 nm against blank. All the formulations were found within specified limit of drug content. Drug content uniformity results were shown in table. no 11.

F. In vitro Drug Release Studies

In vitro drug release studies of samples were carried out by using Franz diffusion cell. Dialysis membrane previously soaked in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer was taken and placed in between donor and receptor compartments. In the donor compartment 1gm of formulation was added. Volume of the diffusion medium was maintained 25 ml in receptor compartment and temperature maintained at $34 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$, and rpm was maintained at 25 by using hot plate magnetic stirrer. Aliquots were withdrawn at intervals of 30, 60, 120 min....up to 6hours and replaced by equal volumes of diffusion medium. Aliquots were suitably diluted with pH 7.4 and analyzed by UV Spectrophotometer at 233 nm. F4 shows 98% of drug release within 6 hours.^[8] The in vitro release of various formulations are shown in the fig. (12, 13, 14).

G. Determination of stability study of formulations

The international conference on harmonization (ICH) harmonized tripartite guide lines on stability testing of new drug substances and product was issued on 27, 1993. The best two formulated cream were filled in the collapsible tubes and stored at different temperature condition viz. $25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} / 60\% \text{ RH} \pm 5\% \text{ RH}$, $30^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} / 65\% \text{ RH} \pm 5\% \text{ RH}$, $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} / 75\% \text{ RH} \pm 5\% \text{ RH}$ for a period of two months and studied for color, appearance and Ph⁹. The stability of best two formulations are given in the table no 16,17,18.

H. Skin Irritation Test

The animals selected are rabbits and guinea pigs. These animals were kept in different cages and supplied with fresh food and water during the test period, 24hours prior to test, the hair from the neck and thigh region was shaved to expose sufficient large test area. The test site was cleaned with surgical spirit then vanishing cream base is applied to test area. The test site was observed for erythema and edema for 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs after application. This test was conducted to evaluate the irritancy of the prepared cream on the intact skin of animals. None of the prepared medicated cream showed any erythema or edema, indicating that the prepared formulations were non-irritant on the skin of animals.^[9]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation Studies

A. Organoleptic properties

The organoleptic properties of drug were found like color, odor, taste, crystallinity and the observations are found to be similar as given in the reference¹⁰. The results are shown in the table 2.

Table 2: Organoleptic properties of drug.

Parameters	Results
Color and physical appearance	White off crystalline powder
Odor	Characteristic Odor
Taste	Characteristic

B. Melting point

The melting point of drug sample was determined by using melting point apparatus. The melting point was found to be in the range of 1320C, which is found to be similar as given in the reference.^[10] The melting point of Salicylic Acid is shown in the table 3.

Table 3: Melting Point.

Drug	Observed	R Reference
Salicylic Acid	158 ⁰ C	157-159 ^o

C. Partition coefficient

The LogP value of salicylic acid was found be 2.15 which shows the lipophilic nature of drug.^[10] The value is recorded in the table 4.

Table 4: Partition coefficient value of Salicylic Acid.

Drug	Observed	Reference
Salicylic Acid	2.15	2 .35

D. Identification of drug by

1. UV Spectroscopy

The λ max of Salicylic Acid was obtained at 233 nm. This found to be similar as given in the reference.^[10] Which shows that drug is pure. The UV spectrum of Salicylic Acid drug is shown in the fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Spectrum of salicylic Acid by UV Spectroscopy.

2. Preparation of standard Calibration curve of salicylic acid (λ_{\max} 233nm)

Calibration curve of salicylic acid was prepared in methanol at 233 nm. The absorbance values (mean of three determinations) with their standard deviation at different concentration in the range of 5-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for pH 7.4 phosphate buffer are tabulated. The drug obeys Beer's Lambert law in the concentration range. Linear regression analysis for all calibration curves of salicylic acid is given in Table. So, this equation was used for the calculation of the solubility of the drug in different solvent, drug content and drug release. The calibration curve of salicylic acid is shown in fig. 6.

Fig 6: Calibration curve of salicylic acid.

E. Solubility studies of drug

Solubility studies for the drug Salicylic Acid were performed and explained as follow:

1. Qualitative solubility study

Qualitative solubility analysis for drug Salicylic Acid was determined in different solvents. The Salicylic Acid was found to be slightly soluble in methanol, octanol and PEG 400 and soluble in propylene glycol and PEG 400. This shows that drug is soluble only in organic solvents, which shows the lipophilic nature of the drug. The results are found to be similar as given in the reference¹¹. Results are disclosed in the table 7.

Table 7: Qualitative solubility study in various solvents.

S.no	Solvents	Solubility
1.	Water	Insoluble
2.	Methanol	Slightly soluble
3.	Octanol	Slightly soluble
4.	Propylene Glycol	Soluble
5.	PEG	Soluble
6.	Chloroform	Slightly soluble

2. Quantitative solubility study

Quantitative solubility analysis of Salicylic Acid was determined in different solvents. The Salicylic Acid drug was found to be more soluble in Methanol, propylene glycol and PEG 400 and chloroform. This shows that drug is soluble only in organic solvents, which shows the lipophilic nature of the drug. The results are found to be similar as given in the reference.^[12] The results are disclosed in table 8.

Table 8: Quantitative solubility analysis.

S.no	Solvents	Solubility mg/ml
1.	Water	2.24 mg/mL
2.	Methanol	3.45 mg/ml
3.	Octanol	4.55 mg/ml
4.	Propylene Glycol	3.67 mg/ml
5.	PEG	3.78 mg/ml
6.	Chloroform	3.12 mg/ml

Results of Evaluation

A. Physical Examination

The organoleptic characters of all the formulations are as follow:

Table 9: Organoleptic characters.

Batch code	COLOR	ODOR	APPEARANCE
F1	White	Odorless	Good
F2	White	Odorless	Good

F3	White	Odorless	Good
F4	White off	Odorless	Excellent
F5	White off	Odorless	Excellent

B. Determination of pH of ointment formulation

The pH of all the formulations are found in the range of 5.4 to 6.4. The pH of formulations are as follow:

Table 10: pH of ointment formulation.

Batch code	pH
F1	5.4
F2	5.6
F3	5.9
F4	6.4
F5	6.4

C. Rheological Properties

The viscosity of all the formulations were found the range of 24600 to 28996, which was similar as given in the reference.^[13] The viscosity of all the formulations are given as

Table 11: Viscosity of formulations.

Batch code	Viscosity (cps)
F1	26800
F2	25900
F3	24600
F4	28010
F5	28996

D. Spreadability

The spreadability was found in the range of 31 to 36 which was found to be similar as given as given in the reference.^[14] The spreadability of all the formulations are as follow:

Table 12: Spreadability of formulations.

Batch code	Spreadability (g.cm/sec)
F1	31
F2	33
F3	34
F4	36
F5	35

E. Drug content: The drug content estimation was performed to ensure uniform distribution of drug. The drug content of salicylic acid vanishing cream was performed for all the

prepared formulations. The result indicates that the drug content in all the formulations was found uniform between 89% to 97% which was scanned spectrophotometrically at λ_{max} 233 nm. The drug content of various formulations is recorded in table 13.

Table 13: Drug content of various formulations.

S.NO	Formulation Code	% Drug content
1.	F1	89%
2.	F2	90%
3.	F3	92%
4.	F4	97%
5.	F5	96%

F. In vitro drug release studies

The in vitro drug release profile of pure drug, formulated ointment preparations in dissolution medium are shown in figure (14, 15, 16). Formulated vanishing cream of salicylic acid showed a significant increase in the drug release as compared with pure salicylic acid. In the formulations F1 and F2 showing 92.3% and 91.4% drug release, F3 and F4 showing 93.4% and 93.7% drug release, and F5 and F6 showing 96.4% and 97.6% drug release respectively. All the formulation shows improved drug release rate as compared to pure salicylic acid.

Figure 14: Comparison of In- vitro release of pure salicylic acid & F1, F2 Batches.

Figure 15: Comparison of In- vitro release of pure salicylic acid & F3, F4 Batches.

Figure 16: Comparison of In-vitro release of pure salicylic acid & F5 Batch.

G. Determination of stability study of formulations.

The stability of best two formulations was studied as per ICH guideline for 2 months. The stability studies shows only minor change in pH, which prove that the formulations are stable. The stability of all the formulations are shown in the table 17,18,19.

Table 17: Stability parameters.

Parameter (after 15 days)	Formulation F4			Formulation F5		
	25 ⁰ C	30 ⁰ C	40 ⁰ C	25 ⁰ C	30 ⁰ C	40 ⁰ C
Appearance	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent
Color	White off					
pH	6.4	6.4	6.3	6.5	6.5	6.4

Table 18: Stability Parameters.

Parameter (after 30 days)	Formulation F4			Formulation F5		
	25 ⁰ C	30 ⁰ C	40 ⁰ C	25 ⁰ C	30 ⁰ C	40 ⁰ C
Appearance	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent
Color	White off					
pH	6.4	6.4	6.3	6.5	6.5	6.4

Table 19: Stability Parameters.

Parameter (after 15 days)	Formulation F4			Formulation F5		
	25 ⁰ C	30 ⁰ C	40 ⁰ C	25 ⁰ C	30 ⁰ C	40 ⁰ C
Appearance	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent
Color	White off					
pH	6.4	6.4	6.3	6.5	6.5	6.4

H. Skin Irritation Test

The present study tries to focus the array of his to morphological changes of skin of rabbits after application of vanishing cream formulations to examine the skin irritation. The results obtained were shown photographically. Comparison of the photographic images of control (before application) as against the photographic images of skin after application of formulation has shown no detectable tissue damage resulting from the exposure to the cream formulations. Redness, erythema or inflammation were not been detected. Photographic images have shown no significant difference between the two images on comparison between before and after application. Even on visually examining after each application no much difference could be identified. Thus, indicates the vanishing cream formulation passes the primary skin irritation test.

Table 20: Skin Irritation Test.

Formulation code	Rabbits	Before application			After 24hrs. of application			After 48 hrs. of application			After 72 hrs. of application		
		I	R	E	I	R	E	I	R	E	I	R	E
F1	Male-I	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Male-II	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Female	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
F2	Male-I	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Male-II	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Female	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
F3	Male-I	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Male-II	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Female	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
F4	Male-I	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Male-II	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Female	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
F5	Male-I	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Male-II	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Female	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

I- Skin irritation, R-redness,

E-Erythema

CONCLUSION

The vanishing cream preparations of salicylic acid are designed using different bases for the treatment of skin psoriasis. During our physicochemical evaluation studies all the formulations were found to have good spreadability and viscosity. pH determination shows that all the formulation have near neutral pH and does not changed during the study period. Hence, there was no possibility of any kind of skin irritation. The drug content estimation showed uniform drug content in the all prepared formulations. *In-Vitro* drug release studies shows that, the formulation code F3 showed optimum release (51.28%) in 3 hours. In our present investigation of stability studies, all prepared formulations did not segregate, ferment or physically deteriorated during storage and use at ambient temperature (30°C) for the period of six months. All the formulations did not undergo phase separation or gassing fermentation or otherwise deterioration anesthetically. Skin irritation test were carried out on both laboratory experimental animal (Rabbit). The studies revealed that the usage of vanishing cream bases formulations did not produce skin irritancy. On the observation no edema, erythema, inflammation or redness seen on the skin of both animals and human volunteers indicating formulations pass in the test of compatibility studies. From our study it is revealed that salicylic acid vanishing cream formulation should be useful for treatment of scalp

psoriasis. In contrast with ointments which are greasy and messy in nature and may causes staining of cloths, vanishing cream is pleasant, easily washed by water with increase patient compliance.

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